

GCMS study of petroleum spirit fraction of *Leucas hyssopifolia* Benth.

(Mrs.) G. Bisht* and (Miss) B. Joshi

Department of Chemistry, Kumaon University, Nainital-263 002, India

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Fourteen aliphatic long-chain hydrocarbons from heptadecane to hexacosane and nine aliphatic ethyl esters ethyl tetradecanoate to ethyl heneicosanoate, have been isolated and identified by GC-MS study in petroleum spirit fraction of *Leucas hyssopifolia*.

The plant *Leucas hyssopifolia* Benth. is a perennial herb and grows usually in rock crevices, newly formed walls and grasslands ascending to 909 m in the subtropical region¹. It is reported to possess antibacterial and antifungal activities². The present paper reports the identification of aliphatic hydrocarbons and esters in the petroleum spirit fraction of this plant by GCMS study.

The roots of *L. hyssopifolia*, collected from Katarmal,

Almora, in September 1995, were dried, powdered and extracted in a Soxhlet with 80% aq. ethanol for ~16 h. The extract was concentrated and the concentrate re-extracted with chloroform . water (50 : 50) for 8 h. The chloroform fraction was concentrated and the residue obtained was extracted with petroleum spirit. The spirit-soluble portion was evaporated to residue which was chromatographed over silica gel G column and eluted with petroleum spirit. A small frac-

Table 1 GCMS of Fraction-1

Sl no	Ret time min	%	Mol ion (M ⁺) m/z	Other fragments m/z	Compound identified
1	37 48	0 83	240	43, 57(100%), 71, 85, 99, 113	Heptadecane
2	40 98	10 54	252	43, 57, 69, 83(100%), 97,111, 125	Octadecene
3	41 22	1 83	254	43, 57(100%), 71, 85, 99, 113	Octadecane
4	44 55	1 49	268	43, 57(100%), 71, 85, 99, 113	Nonadecane
5	47 72	11 93	280	43, 57, 69, 83, 97(100%), 111, 125	Eicosene
6	47 87	1 34	282	43, 57(100%), 71, 85	Eicosane
7	50 93	0 95	296	43, 57(100%), 71, 85, 99	Heneicosane
8	53 75	7 72	308	57, 69, 83, 97(100%), 111, 125	Docosene
9	53 95	1 05	310	57(100%), 71, 85, 99, 113	Docosane
10	56 78	1 64	324	57(100%), 71, 85, 99, 113, 127	Tricosane
11	59 38	4 19	336	57, 69, 83, 97(100%), 111, 125	Tetracosene
12	59 53	3 04	338	57(100%), 71, 85, 99	Tetracosane
13	62 47	4 22	352	57(100%), 71, 85, 99, 113, 127	Pentacosane
14	66 17	2 58	366	57(100%), 71, 85, 99, 113, 127	Hexacosane

Table 2 GCMS of Fraction-2

Sl no	Ret time	%	Mol ion (M ⁺) m/z	Other fragments m/z	Compound identified
1	40 93	0 43	256	75, 88(100%), 101, 175, 213	Ethyl tetradecanoate
2	44 37	0 23	270	75, 88(100%), 143, 157, 213, 227	Ethyl pentadecanoate
3	48 12	30 30	284	73, 88(100%), 157	Ethyl hexadecanoate
4	50 85	2 07	298	73, 88(100%), 101, 143, 157, 213, 255	Ethyl heptadecanoate
5	53 12	5 63	310	55, 69, 88(100%), 97, 101, 137, 155, 222, 264	Ethyl octadecenoate
6	53 98	7 50	312	88(100%), 101, 137, 143, 213, 227, 269	Ethyl octadecanoate
7	56 63	0 70	326	73, 88(100%), 101, 157	Ethyl nonadecanoate
8	59 38	6 23	340	73, 88(100%), 143, 157, 213, 255	Ethyl icosanoate
9	66 02	6 22	368	73, 88(100%), 101, 157, 325	Ethyl heneicosanoate

Note

tion (25 ml) was eluted and tested by tlc. The elutes (frs. 1–9), obtained as a mixture of hydrocarbons, were mixed and labelled fraction-1. The elutes (frs. 10–15) showing similar tlc results were mixed and labelled fraction-2 which was analysed by GCMS in a Hewlett-Packard 5840 A GC interfaced with a Hewlett-Packard 5985 mass spectrometer (initial temp. 60°, final temp. 240° and programming rate 2°/min). The mass spectral data corresponding to the GC peaks were analysed and the compounds were identified by comparison of the mass spectra with the reference spectra available³

Fraction-1 was found to be a mixture of 14 aliphatic long-chain hydrocarbons (Table 1) which amounted to only ~53% of this fraction. Fraction-2 was found to be a mixture of aliphatic ethyl esters (Table 2) which also amounted to only 59.3% of this fraction. The rest of the materials in each fraction could not be characterised.

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